

POLICY BRIEF

ACHIEVE GOOD ECOLOGICAL STATUS OF SURFACE WATERS BY 2027 AND BEYOND

Why authorities should use citizen science to meet targets and strengthen public engagement

In a Nutshell

Achieving good ecological status of surface waters by 2027 remains a major challenge. In 2021, only 39.5% of EU surface water bodies were reported in good or high ecological status. Not a single country was reported to be on track to achieve compliance. Citizen science can complement official monitoring, identify pollution hotspots and strengthen local stewardship. Integrating citizen science into the implementation of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Program of Measures (PoM) can enable authorities to meet targets and ensure sustainable water management in the longer term.

Policy context

The EU and its Member States have long been committed to achieving good ecological status of surface waters. The Water Framework Directive (WFD) sets December 2027 as the deadline. According to the latest report on the state of water in the EU, however, only 39.5% of EU surface water bodies are achieving good ecological status. Progress remains insufficient, making successful Programs of Measures, especially to reduce nutrient pollution under the Nitrates Directive, a continuing priority.

The recently published Water Resilience Strategy reinforces this commitment and foresees dialogues with Member States to ensure sustainable water management across Europe. This is an opportunity to review progress and plans under the WFD.

Policy challenge

Many authorities struggle to meet ecological standards and have limited monitoring resources, particularly for small streams and minor water bodies.

Alert systems for pollution events are often insufficient. Public awareness of best practices for water management remains limited, restricting community support and compliance.

How can national and local authorities involved in implementing the WFD and the Nitrates Directive rise to the 2027 challenge? And, beyond that, put in place the necessary measures to ensure the continued achievement of good ecological status?

Citizens can make a difference

Citizen science can provide a complementary approach to official efforts, enhancing data coverage and strengthening public engagement. This can increase the likelihood of achieving and maintaining good ecological status. It can produce high-quality, scientifically robust data that complements official monitoring. Measurements and observations by citizen scientists who receive proper training, follow standardised protocols, and use validated methods are reliable and actionable. Such citizen generated data enhances monitoring coverage of small streams and minor water bodies.

Citizens can provide more frequent measurements and

support early-warning systems that detect pollution events or emerging hotspots quickly.

During targeted campaigns, citizens can highlight major pollution differences and their samples can be sent to high-quality labs, like the for instance the Big Windermere Survey.

Beyond monitoring, citizen engagement raises public awareness and strengthens local stewardship because social learning helps spread best practices beyond the participants themselves, via family members, neighbours, farmers and local organisations.

Course of Action

Most official monitoring under the WFD is designed to assess ecological status, not to evaluate how effective the resulting measures are. Monitoring is often insufficient in frequency and poorly aligned with the locations where impacts should be assessed.

We call on national and local authorities to integrate citizen science into the monitoring of Program of Measures under River Basin Management Plans (RBMP), complementing WFD surveillance and operational monitoring.

For instance, Annex V of the WFD states that ‘Operational monitoring shall be undertaken [...] in order to [...] establish the presence of any long term anthropogenically induced upward trend in the concentration of any pollutant.’

The Directive does not foresee a requirement to monitor any downward trend in pollution due to RBMP measures. This is a major flaw as evidence to evaluate the effectiveness of restoration measures is not collected. Citizen science could fill this knowledge gap.

Voices on the ground

The Netherlands

Koenraad Backers
Program lead Water at Natuur en Milieu

“Including citizens in research projects builds support for the implementation of governance solutions. It helps train citizens into knowledgeable debaters that can vocalize local arguments. This reinforces water governance practices such as monitoring programs, subsidies, and new regulations. By mobilizing involved citizens, they can create valuable insights in the ecological status of surface water, and it enables people to help improve the local water quality.”

Reach out to us!

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